

Inspection of Maximum Power Point Tracking Methods Suitable for Low-Power Electronics

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Abstract— This paper presents inspection of direct and indirect Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms suitable for low-power applications. Theoretically, indirect algorithms are faster than direct ones, however less efficient in power extraction. Among both types, we chose one of the simplest and the most used algorithms. Open Circuit Voltage and Perturb and Observe (P&O) methods were selected. During the testing of Energy Harvester (EH) controlled by MPPT algorithms, we focused on parameters such as accuracy of reaching the Maximum Power Point (MPP), deviation from the MPP and speed of convergence. We found that the direct MPPT algorithm is more suitable for low power applications under various conditions, because it is 1.6 times faster and the deviation from MPP is 4.12 times smaller.

Index Terms— MPPT, Open Circuit Voltage, Perturb and Observe, Pilot-Cell, Energy Harvester

I. INTRODUCTION

The ongoing research and development in electronics, especially in the field of integrated circuits, naturally increases the demands on electronic devices. In recent years, the market has significantly expanded with sensor systems connected to the Internet of Things (IoT) and wearable devices, where the main issue is no longer the lack of computing power but the way of power supplying and the energy consumption [1], [2]. The most common power source for such systems are batteries, which are significantly limited by their lifespan. Using the energy harvester can extend the battery life or completely replace them [3]. Energy harvester is an electronic system that harvests an ambient energy, converts it into electrical energy using an energy converter (EC), and further adjusts it using a DC-DC voltage converter (VC). Due to the dynamic changes in the input and output of the EH, the system is not able to operate on its own in terms of output power and efficiency, therefore it needs the presence of an auxiliary control circuit that seeks the maximum power point. In general, this is the process of eliminating the mismatch between the output impedance of energy converter in MPP and input impedance of energy harvester. MPPT algorithm then ensures the maximum power extraction from EC [4]. There are several methods or

algorithms by which it is possible to approach or reach the maximum power point. We can categorize them into indirect and direct algorithms.

Indirect algorithms excel in their simplicity and speed, on the other hand they operates with many constant values, what negatively affects the efficiency of the energy harvester. One can say that direct algorithms are the exact opposite of indirect algorithms, because direct algorithms work with variables and they can be very precise in reaching the maximum power point. On the other hand, these properties have negative impact on circuit complexity, computing speed and energy consumption. However, it cannot be said that indirect algorithms are worse and direct ones are better. There is no single perfect MPPT algorithm for a wide range of circuits, and choosing the best one is highly application dependent. At the Department of integrated circuit design and test (ONTIO), we have developed a prototype of the on-chip EH that can be externally connected to the Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) with different types of MPPT algorithms to control the system operation. This solution extends the system versatility by modification of MPPT algorithms during testing the EH system. This possibility gives a huge space in different subject curriculum or aim of bachelor and master theses.

II. MPPT ALGORITHMS

The most common source for energy harvesters is solar energy. It is converted into electricity using photovoltaic (PV) cells. Although, the power-voltage (P-V) characteristic of a PV cell is nonlinear in typical conditions, it has only one global maximum as it is depicted in Figure 1. When the operating point (OP) is located at the highest point on the P-V curve, we say that the energy converter is in MPP and the maximum possible energy extraction from the input to output occurs. The position of operating point on the P-V curve is determined by the input and output conditions of the energy converter that is an uncontrolled process. Therefore, the operating point

Fig. 1. P-V characteristics under typical conditions.

of the system must be influenced by an additional control circuit based on MPPT algorithms that alters EH operation. MPPT algorithms can be divided into two categories based on sensing of input/output conditions (or system configuration) and operating point (OP) position on the P-V curve:

- Indirect algorithms
- Direct algorithms

A. Indirect algorithms

Indirect MPPT algorithms use derived quantities as constants to approximately evaluate the position of the OP in relation with MPP. They are based on multiple methods, including manipulation of system voltage, temperature measurement, and calculating the voltage at MPP by measuring the open circuit voltage [5], [6]. Based on these quantities, a reference voltage or current is calculated as expected value at the solar cell output. The main advantages of indirect MPPT algorithms are their simplicity and speed. However, the most crucial disadvantage here is inaccuracy, which can lead to sub-optimal energy extraction.

B. Direct algorithms

The direct algorithms use information about the operating point position of the photovoltaic cell, usually by measuring the direct voltage and current value at the input of energy harvester to dynamically adjust OP as close to the MPP as possible. The algorithm determine the position of OP based on the comparison current and previous measurement, and decides in which direction has to be moved (e.g., voltage increase or decrease) on the P-V curve of the photovoltaic cell. In comparison to indirect methods, the biggest advantage of direct MPPT algorithms is higher accuracy and their ability to adapt the various external conditions that influence the position of MPP on the P-V curve (e.g., illumination, temperature, aging of the photovoltaic cell). The disadvantage is their higher hardware complexity what leads to extra demands on chip area and power consumption.

III. OPTIMAL MPPT ALGORITHM FOR LOW-POWER APPLICATIONS

Selecting the most suitable MPPT algorithm for energy harvesting in low-power applications, two critical parameters must be considered. The first parameter is the power consumption of the MPPT algorithm itself, which should be as small as possible. The second one is the efficiency of MPPT algorithm, what indicates how much energy the harvester can harvest compared to designs working with other algorithms. The decision of choosing the right MPPT algorithm based on information mentioned above is not simple. One of the most basic indirect MPPT algorithm is the Open Circuit Voltage (OCV). It compares the photovoltaic cell output voltage with a reference voltage and adjust parameters of DC-DC converter until the output voltage matches the reference voltage. The flowchart of OCV algorithm is depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. OCV algorithm flowchart.

The reference voltage is typically set to app. 76 % of the open circuit voltage of the photovoltaic cells (value usually available in datasheet of solar cell), what is usually close to MPP [5]. The key issue for OCV algorithm is knowing the open-circuit voltage value. It can be acquired by disconnecting the photovoltaic cell from subsequent circuit or using pilot cell to only provide the open-circuit voltage value. The first approach is impractical because in some applications where all circuits are powered solely by photovoltaic cells, the entire system would have to shut down during obtaining OCV value. In the second approach, there are used two identical and closely placed PV cells. The first one is used for providing energy for the entire system, while the second one is used to obtain OCV voltage. This requires double area while maintaining the same power output levels. In case of the second approach, this reference part could occupy

up to half of the available photovoltaic surface, leading to decreased efficiency. Direct MPPT algorithms are generally more efficient at tracking the MPP where the environmental conditions (such as illumination, temperature or partial shading of the photovoltaic cells) can vary. Direct MPPT algorithm based on Perturb and Observe (P&O) approach can react to change in the environmental conditions and it is considered highly efficient and well known in practice [7]. The flowchart of P&O algorithm is depicted in Figure 3. Their main disadvantage is the necessity of using an Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) for measuring changes in power and voltage values at the input of energy harvester that increases the demand on power consumption. After reviewing several indirect and direct MPPT algorithms, the two types mentioned above were selected for the specified research purposes.

Fig. 3. P&O algorithm flowchart.

IV. TESTING MPPT ALGORITHMS

Within the designed fully on-chip EH (implemented in a form of ASIC) depicted in Figure 4, we also proposed control circuit based on OCV MPPT algorithm, due to its simplicity [8]. The developed system uses two equivalent solar

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the proposed EH system.

cells. The first one is providing energy to EH and the second one serve as information source for the control circuit. There is no need to use ADC converter since it can be replaced by a comparator. The comparator generates digital 1-bit information based on the comparison of OCV value and reference voltage value of MPP (that)is around 76 % of OCV). The MPPT processes 1-bit information and based on that determines the direction of the operating point move on the P-V curve.

On the proposed full-custom chip (ASIC), we implemented the OCV MPPT algorithm, whose input is a Boolean value from an external comparator. We also designed adaptation circuits on the chip so that it is possible to externally connect the FPGA to integrated energy harvester, and in this way, we can upload other modified existing algorithms or completely new ones. Using the FPGA board, we tested the following MPPT algorithms:

- **OCV** - Indirect MPPT algorithm, clone of the algorithm implemented on the chip uploaded to the FPGA board for easier modification of the test setup. Algorithm is based on the flowchart shown in Figure 2.
- **P&O** - Direct MPPT algorithm based on the flowchart shown in Figure 3. Used P&O algorithm requires only one solar cell and its output voltage and current are sensed by pair of two-channel external ADCs. The output ADC value is transmitted with I2C protocol to the FPGA and processed by implemented P&O algorithm. Based on received voltage and current values, it generates a data word to adjust operating point on the P-V curve of PV cell. The block diagram of externally connected circuit to the chip is depicted in Figure 5. The finite-state machine (FSM) block is only used to provide data conversion between I2C and MPPT block.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of energy harvester connected with FPGA.

V. DEFINING PARAMETERS

For the two algorithms under comparison, we defined three parameters to be examined under various illumination conditions and for multiple sizes of incremental steps. Firstly, it is necessary to define what constitutes the convergence of algorithm. It is characterized by periodic oscillations around the convergence power point, which could represents either the MPP or a false MPP of the system under partially shaded

conditions. Convergence is defined to start at the time point (expressed in clock cycles), where the power output equals 99% of the maximal power output in a measurement run, as shown in Figure 6. The first parameter represents whether

Fig. 6. Explanation of compared parameters

the algorithm reached MPP, which indicates that the point of convergence is the actual MPP. The second parameter is the standard deviation, which means how much the power fluctuates in the state of convergence and thus, how far it moves from the optimum point. The third parameter is the time needed to reach the convergence (expressed in clock cycles), which represents the algorithm's flexibility in response to the illumination changes. All parameters were examined under various illumination conditions. Lighting conditions were provided by an LED panel placed in a box, driven by a current source ranging from 200 mA to 450 mA (which corresponding to an irradiance of 288.1 W/m² to 544.8 W/m²). For comparison, the values of solar irradiance at the high noon in direct sunlight approach to 1000 W/m² [9]. Measurements at lower irradiance levels were not performed because the output power of the photovoltaic cell was insufficient for the on-chip DC-DC converter to operate properly. All algorithms were tested under the same initial conditions to reach convergence. The divider for the reference voltage was derived from the open circuit voltage value for the OCV MPPT and it was set to an irradiance of 402 W/m² that is approximately in the middle of measured range.

VI. TEST SETUP

Data for comparison of the MPPT algorithms were acquired using the testing setup shown in Figure 7. The solar cell was placed in a dark box and irradiated by LED panels. The examined MPPT algorithms were implemented to the FPGA. Two Fluke 8845A multimeters were used to acquire the output voltage and current of the PV cell. Data were transferred to a computer over TCP/IP communication protocol. Internal variables of the FPGA were sent to the computer via USB using the UART protocol, where they were processed with the data taken from multimeters in LabVIEW software.

Fig. 7. Workplace for measuring properties of proposed EH system

Both algorithms were tested with various fixed step sizes (1, 3, 5, 10) as well as the adaptive step size that autonomously changes during the process of MPPT algorithm. The adaptive step size feature of the implemented algorithm adjusts the step size according to the magnitude change in supply power value. Step size represents the change in voltage value between two subsequent operating points, with values ranging from 0.015 mV to 22.1 mV. This variability is caused by nonlinear relationship between settings of the DC-DC converter and the output voltage of the PV cell as shown in Figure 8, where the x-axis represents the serialized values configured on the M3M and CS registers, which define the operating conditions of the DC-DC converter. The y-axis indicates the voltage values measured at the output of the photovoltaic cell.

VII. ACHIEVED RESULTS

Both algorithms were successful in achieving the maximum power point of the system, with one exception. The P&O algorithm with too small step size (P&O 1) failed to do so. This failure was due to small perturbations that the change in output power was below the sensitivity of ADC converter used to measure the output voltage and current of the PV cell.

Fig. 8. Relationship between the registers CS and M3M, and the voltage at the output of the PV cell.

TABLE I
ACHIEVED RESULTS OF VCO AND P&O MPPT ALGORITHMS

Irradiation	288.1 W/m ²			349.7 W/m ²			404.5 W/m ²		
	Algorithm	P _{out} [mW]	ΔP _{out} [mW]	[cycles]	P _{out} [mW]	ΔP _{out} [mW]	[cycles]	P _{out} [mW]	ΔP _{out} [mW]
OCV Adapt	10.0188	0.4901	3	12.5460	0.5799	6	14.9331	0.6244	7
OCV 1	10.2445	0.1604	165	12.8446	0.1566	232	15.1874	0.2405	245
OCV 3	10.2033	0.2045	56	12.7433	0.1866	78	15.0105	0.3659	83
OCV 5	10.1807	0.2634	34	12.7698	0.2402	48	14.9153	0.5981	51
OCV 10	10.1289	0.2542	18	12.6151	0.2919	25	14.8168	0.5334	29
P&O Adapt	10.0531	0.0410	19	12.5484	0.0288	28	14.9576	0.0857	34
P&O 1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P&O 3	10.0915	0.0581	27	12.5794	0.0414	37	14.9209	0.0552	42
P&O 5	10.0616	0.0299	17	12.5277	0.0364	22	14.8515	0.0367	25
P&O 10	10.1245	0.0401	9	12.6271	0.0645	11	15.0060	0.0467	13
Irradiation	454.6 W/m ²			501.8 W/m ²			544.8 W/m ²		
Algorithm	P _{out} [mW]	ΔP _{out} [mW]	[cycle]	P _{out} [mW]	ΔP _{out} [mW]	[cycle]	P _{out} [mW]	ΔP _{out} [mW]	[cycle]
OCV Adapt	17.3391	0.4528	10	19.5168	0.3114	12	21.5016	0.3957	12
OCV 1	17.4173	0.1951	274	19.5738	0.2073	304	21.5101	0.2477	311
OCV 3	17.3486	0.2463	95	19.4673	0.2674	104	21.4712	0.2646	105
OCV 5	17.3755	0.3701	58	19.5735	0.2636	64	21.4405	0.4017	63
OCV 10	17.3369	0.1877	31	19.4311	0.2616	34	21.4051	0.3163	34
P&O Adapt	17.1164	0.0434	38	19.1576	0.0696	184	21.1199	0.0549	36
P&O 1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P&O 3	17.1028	0.0578	47	19.1615	0.1023	52	21.0969	0.0635	54
P&O 5	17.0207	0.0795	28	19.1219	0.1155	31	21.0933	0.0922	33
P&O 10	17.1899	0.1861	14	19.1751	0.2522	16	21.1781	0.1665	17

All obtained results (output power P_{out}, standard deviation ΔP_{out} and number of cycles required to reach convergence) are summarized in the Table I. Standard deviation and number of cycles to reach the convergence are also depicted in Figure 9, where the x-axis represents the convergence time of the algorithm in clock cycles, while the y-axis denotes the standard deviation from the Maximum Power Point (MPP), with a lower standard deviation indicating smaller deviations from MPP, and thus more efficient power extraction. Each data point corresponds to an individual measurement run, with the runs distinguished by color and shape according to the algorithm method and step size, as detailed in the plot legend. Different data points for one algorithm represents different irradiation conditions for each measurement run. All Perturb and Observe P&O based measurement runs are enclosed within a red ellipse, located in the lower-left corner of the plot, which represents the optimal region for Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms, as shown in the plot. In contrast, the Open Circuit Voltage (OCV)-based measurement runs are predominantly outside this region. From the plotted data, it can be observed that P&O algorithm has a significantly smaller standard deviation than algorithms based on the OCV method for comparable step sizes. This leads to P&O algorithm oscillating closer to the real MPP, thus achieving greater efficiency. When comparing algorithms based on the P&O method to those based on the OCV method with the same step size, we can conclude that the P&O-based algorithms are slightly faster than OCV ones. The P&O algorithm with

adaptive step size has the smallest standard deviation. Its speed is slower than that of the P&O algorithm with step sizes of 10 and 5, and the OCV algorithm with step size 10, but the variability of its speed in relation to changes in irradiance conditions is the smallest among all investigated cases. This means that its speed of convergence is less dependent on the value of irradiance. Therefore, the achieved performance of the P&O algorithm with adaptive step size is the most consistent in a wide range of input conditions while achieving very high accuracy and speed of convergence.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A comparison of two MPPT algorithms (OCV and P&O) suitable for low-power energy harvesting in dynamic light conditions was conducted. Three parameters were measured: ability of the algorithm to reach the MPP, standard deviation from the MPP, and the speed of convergence under various irradiance conditions and with varying step sizes for both algorithms. These measurements were executed on a measurement setup composing multimeters and a data acquisition application in LabVIEW. The acquired data show that algorithms based on the P&O method have better stability around the MPP, thus are more efficient and have faster convergence than algorithms based on the OCV method. The average time to convergence and standard deviation for the P&O algorithm was 1.6 times shorter and 4.12 times smaller than that of the OCV-based algorithm, respectively. From the perspective of efficiency in energy extraction from PV

Fig. 9. Comparison of parameters of individual measured algorithms

cells, we can conclude that the P&O-based algorithm appears to be more suitable for low-power applications in dynamic irradiance conditions. For a comprehensive comparison of these two methods, future work should examine the power consumption of the P&O algorithm with all peripheral circuits compared to the power consumption of the OCV algorithm. Only after this comparison, a final conclusion regarding which algorithm is more efficient overall and thus more suitable for this specific application, can be drawn. This paper provides preliminary results about the most important properties of each algorithm with connection to the fully-integrated EH system and provides basis for further student research that can be part of bachelor's or master's theses.

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